

18 **Abstract**

19 *Petasites hybridus* L. (butterbur, Asteraceae) is a well-known medicinal plant traditionally used
20 as a remedy for neurological, respiratory, cardiovascular, and gastrointestinal disorders.
21 Eremophilane-type sesquiterpenes (petasins) are considered to be the major bioactive constituents
22 of butterbur. However, efficient methods to isolate high-purity petasins in sufficient amounts for
23 further analytical and biological testing are lacking. In this study, various sesquiterpenes were
24 separated from a methanol rootstock extract of *P. hybridus* with liquid-liquid chromatography
25 (LLC). The appropriate biphasic solvent system was selected using the predictive thermodynamic
26 model COSMO-RS and shake-flask experiments. After the selection of the feed (extract)
27 concentration and operating flow rate, a batch LLC experiment was performed with *n*-hexane/ethyl
28 acetate/methanol/water 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v). For those LLC fractions containing petasin derivatives
29 with purities <95%, a preparative high-performance liquid chromatography purification step
30 followed. All isolated compounds were identified by state-of-the-art spectroscopic methods, i.e.,
31 liquid chromatography coupled with high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry and nuclear
32 magnetic resonance techniques. As a result, six compounds were obtained, namely 8 β -
33 hydroxyeremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide, 2-[(angeloyl)oxy]eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide, 8 α/β -H-
34 eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide, neopetasin, petasin, and isopetasin. The isolated petasins can be
35 further used as reference materials for standardization and pharmacological evaluation.

36 **Keywords**

37 *Petasites hybridus*; petasin, liquid-liquid chromatography; centrifugal partition chromatography;
38 NMR, LC-HR-MS/MS

39 1. Introduction

40 Butterbur (*Petasites hybridus* L. “G.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb”, bog rhubarb, pestwurz) is a
41 plant of the Asteraceae family distributed throughout Europe, Asia, and North America [1]. *P.*
42 *hybridus* is well known in traditional medicine for its therapeutic valences, e.g., antimigraine, anti-
43 asthmatic, and anti-allergic properties [2]. These activities have been demonstrated in numerous
44 clinical trials [3,4]. The best-established butterbur preparations are extracts of its leaves and
45 rootstocks obtained by subcritical CO₂ extraction. These herbal preparations are recommended for
46 the treatment of seasonal allergies (leaf extracts) and migraine (rhizome extracts) [4,5]. Butterbur
47 extracts contain sesquiterpenes, pyrrolizidine alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic acids, and volatile
48 constituents [1]. Eremophilane-type sesquiterpenes, especially petasin derivatives (e.g., petasin,
49 isopetasin, neopetasin, *S*-petasin, iso-*S*-petasin, neo-*S*-petasin, etc.), are considered to be the active
50 components of butterbur extracts. To date, individual petasin derivatives have been reported to
51 have anti-asthmatic (*via* inhibition of inflammatory mediators) [6], anticancer, and
52 immunomodulatory (*via* cytotoxicity induced in cancer cell lines and inhibition of reactive oxygen
53 species and leucocytes chemotaxis) [7,8], anti-inflammatory (*via* inhibition of cyclooxygenase-2)
54 [9], antimigraine (*via* desensitization of nociceptors by activation of transient receptor potential
55 cation channels A1 and V1) [10], and hypotensive (*via* vasodilatory effects) [11] agents. However,
56 mechanistic data on the activity of individual petasin derivatives are lacking. This may be due to
57 the lack of efficient methods to isolate high-purity petasins with high yield and productivity. To
58 date, the isolation of *P. hybridus* compounds has been performed using conventional
59 chromatographic methods, such as preparative thin-layer chromatography [12] or semi-preparative
60 HPLC [13].

61 Liquid-liquid chromatography (LLC) is a preparative isolation technique increasingly used to
62 separate natural products [14–16]. It is more commonly known as centrifugal partition

63 chromatography (CPC) or countercurrent chromatography (CCC). In LLC, the upper and lower
64 phases of a pre-equilibrated biphasic solvent system are used as the mobile and stationary phases;
65 one of the phases is held stationary by a centrifugal field. The different partitioning of the solutes
66 present in a feed mixture between the two phases results in migration with variable velocities along
67 the column. The separated compounds can be collected at the column outlet. LLC has many
68 advantages over conventional liquid-solid chromatography, such as the absence of irreversible
69 adsorption, which allows virtually complete recovery of the injected sample; lower solvent
70 consumption; relatively lower time expenditure and labor costs, as expensive solid stationary
71 phases or column packing procedures; or the ability to inject raw samples containing compounds
72 with a wide range of polarity [17]. LLC has been applied to isolate various natural products such
73 as polyphenols, alkaloids, terpenoids, coumarins, proteins and peptides [18].

74 To the best of the authors' knowledge, LLC has not previously been used to isolate bioactive
75 compounds from the genus *Petasites*. Nevertheless, sesquiterpenes with structures similar to
76 petasins have been purified using LLC from other plant extracts. For example, two eremophilane-
77 type sesquiterpenes, 8 β -H-eremophil-3,7(11)-dien-12,8 α (15,6 α)-diolide and furanoeremophil-3-
78 en-15,6 α -olide, were isolated from the Chinese medicinal plant *Ligularia atroviolacea* with *n*-
79 hexane/ethyl acetate/ethanol/water 4/1/4/1 (v/v/v/v) [19]. Nootkatone is another example of a
80 sesquiterpene with an eremophilane-like skeleton. Nootkatone has been efficiently purified by LLC
81 with *n*-hexane/methanol/water 5/4/1 (v/v/v) in a batch process or with *n*-hexane/ethyl
82 acetate/methanol/water (HEMWat) 9/1/9/1 (v/v/v/v) using advanced operating modes, such as the
83 trapping multiple dual mode process [20].

84 In the present work, LLC was used as the core separation technology to isolate sesquiterpenes
85 (petasin derivatives) from a *P. hybridus* extract. The biphasic solvent system was selected by
86 combining a computer-aided screening approach based on the predictive thermodynamic model

87 COSMO-RS with shake-flask experiments [21,22]. After selecting the feed (extract) concentration
88 and flow rate, a batch LLC experiment was performed, leading to the separation of several petasin
89 derivatives. All isolated compounds were identified using state-of-the-art spectroscopic methods,
90 i.e., liquid chromatography with high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS/MS) and
91 nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) techniques. Altogether, the computer-aided selection of the
92 biphasic solvent systems, the detailed design of LLC separations, and the use of integrative
93 analytical approaches allowed the fast and efficient separation, isolation, and structural elucidation
94 of sesquiterpenes with complex structures from *P. hybridus* rootstocks.

95 **2. Material and methods**

96 *2.1. Chemicals*

97 Analytical grade *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, 1-propanol, and methanol were purchased from
98 POCH (Gliwice, Poland), whereas chromatographic grade acetonitrile, methanol, and formic acid
99 were provided by J.T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands). Deuterated methanol-*d*₄ (99.96% D)
100 was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Water was purified using a Simplicity[®] water
101 purification system (Millipore, France).

102 *2.2. Plant material and extraction*

103 Dried *P. hybridus* rootstocks were purchased from a pharmacy in Lublin (Poland) and
104 authenticated by one of the authors (Ł.K.). A voucher (01/2021) was kept in the Department of
105 Natural Products Chemistry, Medical University of Lublin. 30 g of the plant material was crushed,
106 ground, and extracted with methanol in a ratio of 1/10 (*w/v*) in an ultrasonic bath three times for 30
107 min (at room temperature). The extracts were filtered, pooled, and evaporated to dryness at low
108 pressure, yielding 4.61 g of dry extract (extraction yield 15.38%).

109 2.3. *Biphasic solvent system preparation*

110 The biphasic solvent systems used in this study consisted of *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, 1-propanol,
111 methanol, and water in various volumetric compositions. To prepare the appropriate system
112 composition, the solvents were mixed in the required volume proportions, shaken vigorously, and
113 equilibrated for at least 2 h at room temperature. A separatory funnel was then used to separate the
114 upper and lower phases, which were transferred to individual glass bottles and then degassed for
115 15 min in an ultrasonic bath before use.

116 2.4. *Selection of the biphasic solvent system*

117 To select the suitable biphasic solvent system, the partition coefficient values of petasin, the
118 representative sesquiterpene lactone from *P. hybridus* extract, were predicted with the
119 thermodynamic model Conductor-Like Screening Model for Realistic Solvents (COSMO-RS) and
120 then validated experimentally in shake-flasks [21,22]. For the COSMO-RS screening, the
121 conformers of all compounds were generated in COSMOconf (Version 4.0, COSMOlogic,
122 Leverkusen, Germany), while the partition coefficients were calculated with COSMOtherm
123 (Version C30 Release 16.01, COSMOlogic, Leverkusen, Germany). A detailed description of the
124 calculation of the partition coefficients with COSMO-RS has been given in previous publications
125 [21–23].

126 For the experimental validation of the best candidate solvent system indicated by the COSMO-
127 RS screening, several mixtures of *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, 1-propanol, methanol, and water were
128 tested in shake-flask experiments. 5 mg of the *P. hybridus* methanolic extract was added to equal
129 volumes (2 mL) of the upper and lower phases of pre-equilibrated solvent systems and shaken
130 vigorously for 2 h in a tube shaker. Then, exactly 1 mL of the upper phase and 1 mL of the lower
131 phase of each solvent system were evaporated to dryness. The residues were then dissolved in 1

132 mL of methanol and analyzed by HPLC. The partition coefficients of each compound (K_i) were
133 calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$134 \quad K_i = \frac{C_i^{UP}}{C_i^{LP}} \quad (1)$$

135 where C_i^{UP} and C_i^{LP} represent the concentrations of the solute i in the upper and lower phases,
136 respectively, determined as described in section 2.8.

137 The separation factor (α) between two compounds i and j was defined as the ratio of their partition
138 coefficients (Eq. 2):

$$139 \quad \alpha_{ij} = \frac{K_j}{K_i} \quad (2)$$

140 where $K_j > K_i$.

141 2.5. Selection of the feed concentration

142 To select the feed concentration for the subsequent LLC experiments, the same procedure as
143 described in section 2.4 was followed with slight modifications. Briefly, increasing amounts (8, 20,
144 40, 100, 200, 300, 400, and 800 mg) of *P. hybridus* extract were added to equal volumes (2 mL) of
145 the upper and lower phases of the pre-equilibrated solvent system and shaken vigorously for 2 h.
146 Then, exactly 1 mL of the upper phase and 1 mL of the lower phase of each solvent system were
147 evaporated to dryness. The residues were then dissolved in 1 mL of methanol and analyzed by
148 HPLC.

149 2.6. Liquid-liquid chromatography experiments

150 2.6.1. Apparatus

151 All LLC experiments were performed on a centrifugal partition chromatography (CPC) unit
152 (CPC250 Classic, Gilson, France) with a column volume of 250 mL. The unit was connected to an

153 AP-MOD-250 mobile phase pump (Gilson, France), a TOY18DAD PDA scanning UV detector
154 (Ecom, Czech Republic), and a fraction collector FC 204 (Gilson, France). The maximum
155 achievable rotation speed is 3000 rpm, and the whole column can be operated at a maximum
156 pressure drop of 100 bar. The feed sample was introduced through a manual injection valve with a
157 volume of 10 mL.

158 2.6.2. Stationary phase retention experiments

159 The flow rate for the subsequent LLC experiments was selected after a series of stationary
160 phase retention experiments performed in descending mode (DSC), with mobile phase flow rates
161 in the range of 6-14 mL/min. For all measurements, the column was first filled with the upper phase
162 of the system under investigation without rotation. The rotation speed was then set to 1700 rpm,
163 and the lower phase was pumped through the column at the intended flow rate for at least one
164 column volume (250 mL). The remaining stationary phase in the column was then displaced by
165 pumping the mobile phase. Stationary phase retention (S_F) was calculated according to Eq. (3):

$$166 S_F = \frac{V_{sp}}{V_c} \quad (3)$$

167 where V_{sp} and V_c represent the stationary phase volume and the total column volume, respectively.
168 A new experiment was performed for each flow rate according to the procedure described above.

169 2.6.3. LLC separation

170 The selected biphasic solvent system (HEMWat 5/1/5/1, v/v/v/v) was prepared as described in
171 section 2.3. The experiment was performed in descending mode (DSC) (lower phase as mobile
172 phase). First, the column was filled with the stationary (upper) phase. Then the rotation was set to
173 1700 rpm, and the mobile (lower) phase was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 10
174 mL/min for 40 min. The injection loop was then loaded with the sample (dry extract dissolved in

175 the lower phase at a concentration of 40 mg/ml). The volume of the displaced stationary phase was
176 measured at the end of the experiment. The fractions were collected every 1 min. Then, exactly 1
177 mL of each fraction was evaporated to dryness, dissolved in 1 mL of methanol, and analyzed by
178 HPLC, as described in section 2.9.1.

179 2.7. Preparative HPLC separation

180 Fractions containing compounds that could not be separated by LLC were pooled, evaporated
181 to dryness, and redissolved in methanol (at a concentration of 40 mg/mL) and further purified by
182 preparative HPLC performed on a Hitachi LaChrom 7000 HPLC system (Hitachi Ltd., Tokyo,
183 Japan) equipped with a D-7000 interface, an L-7150 pump, an L-7420 DAD detector, and an
184 Advantec SF-3120 fraction collector. Experiments were performed on a Cosmosil C18-AR-II
185 column (250 mm × 10 mm, 5 μm) by injecting 50 μL of sample; the mobile phase consisted of 60%
186 acetonitrile for the fraction containing compounds P4, P5, and P6 and 70% methanol for the
187 fractions containing compounds P1 and P2; the flow rate was 3 mL/min, and the effluent was
188 monitored at 230 nm.

189 2.8. Analytical methods

190 2.8.1. HPLC-DAD

191 The crude extract and all collected fractions were analyzed by HPLC-DAD. Separations were
192 performed on a Gemini 5 μm, NX-C18, 110 Å, 250 x 4,6 mm column using a mobile phase prepared
193 from water (A) and methanol (B) with the following gradient: 0 min, 70% B; 32 min, 70% B; 33
194 min, 100% B; 35 min 100% B; 36 min, 70% B; 45 min, 70% B. The flow rate was 1 mL/min, the
195 column temperature was 25°C, the injection volume was 10 μL, and the detection wavelength was
196 set at 230 nm. The concentration of each compound present in the samples was determined from
197 the response factors at 230 nm using a five-point calibration curve obtained with petasin standard

198 (5-100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, $A=26939 \times c - 127680$, $R^2=0.9975$); a similar response factor was assumed for all
199 compounds. All separations were performed in triplicate.

200 2.8.2. LC-HRMS/MS

201 LC-HRMS/MS experiments were performed on an Agilent 1200 HPLC (Agilent Technologies,
202 Santa Clara, CA, USA) coupled to an autosampler (G1329B), a binary pump (G1312C), a column
203 oven (G1316A), and a DAD detector (G1315D). The Agilent G6530B ESI-Q-TOF-MS was
204 equipped with a nitrogen generator, a compressed air generator, and a compressed air cylinder.
205 Separation was performed on a CORTECS T3 column (100 mm \times 2.1 mm, 2.7 μm) using a mobile
206 phase of 0.1% formic acid in water (solvent A) and 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile (solvent B)
207 with the following gradient: 0 min, 8% B; 53 min, 99% B; 55 min, 99% B; 55.01 min, 8% B; and
208 60 min, 8% B. The total analysis time was 60 min, the injection volume was 1 μL , the flow rate
209 was 0.4 mL/min, and DAD spectra were recorded from 200 to 400 nm. ESI-Q-TOF-MS analysis
210 was performed in positive ionization mode with the following settings: mass range 80-1200 m/z ,
211 gas temperature 300 $^\circ\text{C}$, nitrogen flow 10 L/min, nebulizer pressure 35 psi, skimmer 65 V, capillary
212 voltage 3500 V, fragmentor 120 V, and collision energies 20 and 40 eV.

213 2.8.3. NMR

214 The 1D and 2D NMR spectra (^1H , ^{13}C DEPTQ, HSQC, H2BC, HMBC, ^1H - ^1H COSY DQF,
215 NOESY, TOCSY, ROESY, 1D sel-TOCSY, 1D sel-ROESY) were recorded on a Bruker Avance
216 III HD Ascend-500 spectrometer (Bruker BioSpin, Rheinstetten, Germany), equipped with a 5 mm
217 $^1\text{H}\{^{109}\text{Ag}-^{31}\text{P}\}$ broad-band inverse (BBI) probe at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ in deuterated methanol- d_4 (99.96% D).

218 3. Results and Discussion

219 3.1. Preliminary analysis of *P. hybridus* extract

220 The HPLC-DAD chromatogram of a crude methanol extract obtained from the rootstocks of *P.*
221 *hybridus* is shown in Fig. 1. Six petasin derivatives (labeled **P1-P6**) were monitored. Their content
222 in the crude extract was estimated from the elution peaks recorded at 230 nm, using the relative
223 response factors and the calibration curve obtained with petasin standard. Petasin **P5** (11.58 ± 1.60
224 wt.%) was the major compound, followed by **P3** (7.90 ± 1.03 wt.%), **P1** (5.82 ± 0.21 wt.%), **P6**
225 (5.28 ± 0.17 wt.%), **P2** (3.53 ± 0.18 wt.%), and **P4** (2.08 ± 0.64 wt.%).

226 3.2. Selection of the biphasic solvent system

227 One of the most challenging steps in designing LLC separations is screening suitable biphasic
228 solvent systems. The almost infinite variety of possible solvent combinations that make up biphasic
229 liquid systems requires time- and labor-intensive experiments. In addition to traditional trial-and-
230 error or experimental solvent system screening strategies, computational approaches are gaining
231 increasing popularity [24,25]. For example, the conductor-like screening model for real solvents
232 (COSMO-RS) is a fully predictive thermodynamic model that requires only the molecular
233 structures of the solvents and target compounds as input information to calculate the partition
234 coefficients [17]. Several authors have already demonstrated the potential of COSMO-RS in
235 screening and selecting biphasic solvent systems to separate various model compounds or natural
236 products [21,23].

237 In this study, for simplicity, only the partition coefficients of petasin, the representative
238 derivative from *P. hybridus* extracts, were calculated with COSMO-RS in different biphasic solvent
239 systems. The screening aimed to find candidate solvent systems with partition coefficients for the
240 target compounds within or close to the preferred “sweet spot” range ($0.4 < K_i < 2.5$). According

241 to the literature, this range provides optimal resolution, productivity, and solvent consumption in
242 LLC [26]. More than ten biphasic liquid systems containing different solvents typically used in
243 LLC (e.g., hexane, methanol, 1-propanol, acetonitrile, ethanol, ethyl acetate, water, etc.) were
244 screened. The COSMO-RS predicted partition coefficients for petasin were within the range 0.3-
245 1.3 for *n*-hexane/methanol/water 10/7/3-10/9/1 (v/v/v), 0.2-1.0 for *n*-hexane/ethyl
246 acetate/methanol/water 2/1/2/1-5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v) and 0.5-2.6 for *n*-hexane/1-propanol/water 10/7/3-
247 10/9/1 (v/v/v). For example, *n*-hexane/1-butanol/water 10/7/3-10/9/1 (v/v/v) or *n*-
248 hexane/ethanol/water 10/7/3-10/9/1 (v/v/v) were rejected since the predicted values for these
249 systems were higher than 10 or less than 0.1, respectively.

250 Next, the partition coefficients of the six target petasin derivatives (**P1-P6**) were determined by
251 shake-flask experiments in three preselected solvent systems.

252 Table 1 shows that some solvent systems, especially HEMWat 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v), had partition
253 coefficient values for most of the target compounds within the preferred range. Next, the separation
254 factors (α_{ij}) were calculated according to Eq. (2). In general, separation factors higher than 1.5 are
255 targeted in LLC for a good resolution between two adjacent peaks [26]. However, it was found that
256 in all solvent systems, including HEMWat 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v), the separation factors α_{12} , α_{23} , and α_{34}
257 were good, while α_{45} and α_{56} were close to 1. Thus, petasins **P1**, **P2**, and **P3** could be separated
258 from each other, while **P4**, **P5**, and **P6** are expected to co-elute under the same peak.

259 3.3. Selection of the feed concentration

260 For the selection of the feed (*P. hybridus* extract) concentration, the partition equilibria of the
261 unknown target petasins (**P1-P6**) were determined in shake-flask experiments. In Fig. 2, the x- and
262 y-axes represent the concentration of the target compounds in the lower and upper phases of the
263 HEMWat 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v) solvent system, respectively; the total extract concentration in the

264 solvent system is shown as a label next to the point. The partition equilibria of the six petasins can
265 generally be considered linear (K_i values = constant) for a total extract concentration range of 2-75
266 mg/mL. At higher concentrations (75-200 mg/mL), the concentration of the target petasins in the
267 upper phase increased more than their concentration in the lower phase. Thus, at concentrations
268 >75 mg/mL, the partition equilibria of the target petasin derivatives tend to be nonlinear, and the
269 K_i values can no longer be assumed to be constant. Working with feed concentrations outside the
270 linear range can negatively affect the separation performance (e.g., loss of peak resolution and
271 stationary phase). These phenomena can occur due to perturbations in the thermodynamic and
272 hydrodynamic equilibria of the biphasic solvent system [27]. In this study, a concentration of 40
273 mg/mL was chosen for the subsequent LLC experiment with the *P. hybridus* extract. This
274 concentration is in the middle of the above-mentioned linear range of the partition equilibria of the
275 target petasin derivatives (2-75 mg/mL).

276 3.4. Selection of the operating flow rate

277 A series of stationary phase retention experiments were performed with the biphasic solvent
278 system consisting of HEMW at 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v); the flow rate range studied was between 8 mL/min
279 and 16 mL/min. As expected, the retention of the stationary phase, calculated according to Eq. (3),
280 decreased almost linearly with increasing mobile phase flow rate (Fig. 3). In general, better peak
281 resolution is obtained with higher stationary phase retention; values above 0.5 are usually preferred
282 [28]. In the current work, stationary phase retention values higher than 0.6 were achieved at all
283 flow rates investigated. In order to compensate for the loss of the stationary phase due to the
284 disturbance of the thermodynamic and hydrodynamic equilibrium in the column after the feed
285 (sample) injection, a flow rate of 10 mL/min was chosen for the subsequent LLC experiment, which
286 is a typical flow rate for the CPC unit used.

287 3.5. LLC separation

288 In this section, a batch LLC separation performed on a CPC unit (see section 2.6) was discussed.
289 The biphasic solvent system (HEMWat 5/1/5/1, v/v/v/v), flow rate (10 mL/min), and feed
290 concentration (40 mg/mL of *P. hybridus* extract dissolved in the mobile phase) were selected
291 previously (sections 3.2-3.4). The absolute volume of the injection was 10 ml. Fig. 4 shows the
292 reconstructed LLC chromatogram derived from the offline analysis (HPLC-DAD) of the collected
293 fractions, while the online LLC chromatogram is shown in Fig. S1. For simplicity, only the
294 concentration profiles of the six target petasins are shown, although all impurities were monitored
295 by HPLC-DAD. Constituents **P1**, **P2**, and **P3** were pooled into fractions *p1* (15.85 mg), *p2* (9.08
296 mg), and *p3* (7.40 mg), respectively. Compounds **P4**, **P5**, and **P6** co-eluted in a single peak and
297 were pooled as fraction *p4-6* (17.35 mg). However, the purity of the petasin derivatives obtained
298 during the batch LLC process was below 95% as assessed by HPLC-DAD, except for **P3** (Fig. S2)
299 obtained with HPLC-DAD purity >95%. Therefore, a subsequent step of prep-HPLC (section 2.7)
300 was followed to purify the obtained fractions. Thus, compounds **P1** (3.17 mg), and **P2** (0.54 mg)
301 were obtained with a HPLC-DAD purity >99%, while compounds **P4** (0.42 mg), **P5** (2.36 mg),
302 and **P6** (1.94 mg) had individual purities of >95%. Overall, the yield of obtained compounds in
303 relation to the amount of these constituents in the extract was 23.4% for P3, 13.6% for P1, 3.8%
304 for P2, 5% for P4, 5.1% for P5, and 9.2% for P6.

305 3.6. Structure identification

306 Structure identification of the isolated compounds (Fig. 6) was performed using LC-HRMS/MS
307 and NMR techniques. The LC-HRMS/MS analysis of the purified compounds was performed by
308 comparing the spectro-chromatographic data with databases (KNApSack, PubChem) and relevant
309 literature [12,29–31]. The proposed identities, pseudomolecular ions ($[M+H]^+_{exp}$), fragment ions

310 (MS/MS), calculated mass error (Δ) in ppm, and proposed molecular formula (MF) are given in
311 Table 2, whereas the ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR data of the compounds are shown in Table 3.

312 Compound **P1** had the pseudomolecular ion at m/z 251.1657 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$) and fragment ions at
313 233.1562 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2^+$, the loss of H_2O , 18 Da), 187.1660 ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}^+$) and 177.0710 ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}^+$). Its
314 HSQC and HMBC NMR data (Table 3) showed a set of resonances typical for an eremophilane-
315 type sesquiterpene lactone – three CH_3 , five CH_2 , two CH , and five unprotonated C-atoms, which
316 was in good agreement with the published data of 8β -hydroxyeremophilanolide [31]. As mentioned
317 previously [12], the 8β -epimers of eremophilane lactones can be distinguished from the 8α -epimers
318 by the difference in the chemical shifts of the H-atoms of the $\text{CH}_3(14)$ and $\text{CH}_3(15)$ groups (the
319 numbering of $\text{CH}_3(14)$ and $\text{CH}_3(15)$ follows the IUPAC recommendation RF-4.5 URL:
320 <https://iupac.qmul.ac.uk/sectionF/RF45n6.html> (April 26, 2023), the latter resonating at the higher
321 field than those of $\text{CH}_3(14)$ in skeletons with $\text{H}_\alpha\text{-C}(8)$. Accordingly, the observed ^1H -NMR
322 chemical shifts of $\text{CH}_3(15)$ (δ_{H} 1.07) and $\text{CH}_3(14)$ (δ_{H} 0.84) indicated the 8β -hydroxyeremophil-
323 7(11)-en-12,8 α -olide structure of **P1** (Figs. S3-S9).

324 Compound **P2** had the pseudomolecular ion at m/z 333.2077 ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$) and fragment ions at
325 233.1553 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2^+$, the loss of angelic acid, 100 Da), 215.1459 ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2^+$), 163.0772
326 ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2^+$), and 101.0601 ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{O}_2^+$, angelic acid fragment ion). The NMR data of **P2** suggested
327 the presence of an 8β -H-eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide skeleton with methylated but-2-enoate as
328 a side chain, which was identified as an angeloyl (=Z)-2-methylbut-2-enoyl moiety located at C-
329 2 (Figs. S10-S20). As a result, after comparison with literature data [33], the identity of **P2** was
330 determined as 8β -2-[(angeloyl)oxy]eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8 α -olide (or 2-angeloyloxy- 8β -H-
331 eremophilanolide).

332 The LC-HRMS/MS analysis of compound **P3** revealed a pseudomolecular ion at m/z 235.1690
333 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$) and fragment ions at 217.1537 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}^+$, the loss of H_2O , 18 Da), 189.1496 ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}^+$),

334 153.0173 ($C_{11}H_{21}^+$), 135.0673 ($C_{10}H_{15}^+$) and 107.0758 ($C_8H_{11}^+$). Its HSQC (Fig. S24) and HMBC
335 (Fig. S26) NMR data showed two sets of resonances in the ratio of 63/37 (**P3-major**/**P3-minor**)
336 congruent with the structure of eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide, differing mainly in the 1H -NMR
337 chemical shifts of $CH_3(14)$ and $CH_3(15)$ (Figs. S21-S33). Therefore, the structure of **P3-major** was
338 proposed as 8 β -H-eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide (8 β -H-eremophilanolide or eremophilenolide),
339 while **P3-minor** was proposed as 8 α -H-eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide (8 α -H-eremophilanolide or
340 epieremophilenolide), reported previously in *P. japonicus* [34]. Compounds **P1**, **P2**, and **P3** were
341 previously identified and isolated from *P. hybridus* rhizome extract [31].

342 The LC-HRMS/MS analysis of compounds **P4**, **P5**, and **P6** showed similar fragmentation
343 patterns and pseudomolecular ions (at m/z 317.2104, 317.2091, and 317.2123, respectively),
344 suggesting the same molecular formula ($C_{20}H_{28}O_3$). Compounds **P4** and **P5** were identified as the
345 C-7 epimers neopetasin (**P4**) and petasin (**P5**) based on their NMR chemical shifts and nuclear
346 Overhauser effects (Figs. S34-S57). Neopetasin and petasin were previously isolated from the
347 rhizomes of *P. japonicus* [35]. On the other hand, the structure of compound **P6** was confirmed as
348 isopetasin due to the characteristic set of resonances visible in the HSQC (Fig. S62) and HMBC
349 (Fig. S64) spectra [13].

350 4. Conclusion

351 Overall, the current study integrates in an efficient manner preparative chromatographic
352 techniques (i.e., liquid-liquid chromatography, preparative HPLC) with modern analytical
353 platforms (i.e., LC-HRMS/MS, 1D and 2D NMR), allowing the fast and rapid isolation and
354 structural characterization of valuable biologically active compounds from *P. hybridus*. The
355 isolation of six eremophilane sesquiterpenes (petasin derivatives) from a crude methanol rootstock
356 extract of *P. hybridus* using LLC as the core separation technology is reported herein for the first

357 time. The biphasic solvent system (*n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/water 5/1/5/1, v/v/v/v) was
358 selected by combining a computational screening approach based on the predictive thermodynamic
359 model COSMO-RS with a reduced number of shake-flask experiments. The feed (extract)
360 concentration (40 mg/mL) was chosen by determining the partition isotherms of the six target
361 petasins in the mixture, while the operating flow rate (10 mL/min) was selected from a series of
362 stationary phase retention experiments. The batch LLC separation performed under the above-
363 specified conditions allowed the isolation of 8 β -hydroxyeremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide (**P1**), 2-
364 [(angeloyl)oxy]eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide (**P2**), and 8 α/β -H-eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide
365 (**P3**). However, the separation of neopetasin (**P4**), petasin (**P5**), and isopetasin (**P6**) required a
366 second separation step (prep-HPLC), which was also employed to achieve optimal purity for the
367 isolated compounds. The qualitative and quantitative analysis of the isolated petasins were
368 performed using state-of-the-art spectroscopic techniques (i.e., LC-HRMS/MS and NMR). This
369 approach allowed the preliminary determination of the content of monitored compounds, further
370 identification of the structures, and assessment of the efficiency of the isolation process.

371 The isolated compounds can be used as reference materials to standardize, authenticate, and
372 differentiate butterbur-based medicinal products. In addition, the six petasins, which were obtained
373 with high purities in a maximum of two steps (one LLC step and an optional prep-HPLC step), can
374 be tested in *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments and expand the knowledge of the mechanisms of action
375 of butterbur extracts and its constituents. For production purposes, the process can be further
376 optimized and scaled up.

377 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

378 **Łukasz Kulinowski:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing - original draft,
379 Funding acquisition, Project administration. **Simon Vlad Luca:** Conceptualization, Methodology,

380 Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Łukasz Pecio**: Conceptualization,
381 Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft. **Mirjana Minceva**: Writing – review &
382 editing, Supervision. **Krystyna Skalicka-Woźniak**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing -
383 review & editing, Supervision.

384 **Acknowledgements**

385 This study work was financially supported by the National Science Centre, Poland, no
386 2022/45/N/NZ7/02294 (Preludium 21).

387 **Declaration of competing interest**

388 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

389 **References**

- 390 [1] Ł. Kulinowski, S.V. Luca, M. Minceva, K. Skalicka-Woźniak, A review on the ethnobotany,
391 phytochemistry, pharmacology and toxicology of butterbur species (*Petasites* L.), J
392 Ethnopharmacol. (2022) 115263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2022.115263>.
- 393 [2] C. Sadler, L. Vanderjagt, S. Vohra, Complementary, holistic, and integrative medicine:
394 Butterbur, *Pediatr. Rev.* 28 (2007) 235–238. <https://doi.org/10.1542/pir.28-6-235>.
- 395 [3] M. Blosa, J. Uricher, S. Nebel, C. Zahner, V. Butterweck, J. Drewe, Treatment of early
396 allergic and late inflammatory symptoms of allergic rhinitis with *Petasites hybridus* leaf
397 extract (Ze 339): Results of a noninterventional observational study in Switzerland,
398 *Pharmaceuticals* 14 (2021) 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph14030180>.
- 399 [4] R. Oelkers-Ax, A. Leins, P. Parzer, T. Hillecke, H.V. Bolay, J. Fischer, S. Bender, U.
400 Hermanns, F. Resch, Butterbur root extract and music therapy in the prevention of childhood

- 401 migraine: An explorative study, *Eur. J. Pain.* 12 (2008) 301–313.
402 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpain.2007.06.003>.
- 403 [5] R. Käufeler, W. Polasek, A. Brattström, U. Koetter, Efficacy and safety of butterbur herbal
404 extract Ze 339 in seasonal allergic rhinitis: Postmarketing surveillance study, *Adv. Ther.* 23
405 (2006) 373–384. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02850143>.
- 406 [6] K.P. Lee, S. Kang, M.-S. Noh, S.-J. Park, J.-M. Kim, H.Y. Chung, N.K. Je, Y.-G. Lee, Y.-
407 W. Choi, D.-S. Im, Therapeutic effects of S-petasin on disease models of asthma and
408 peritonitis, *Biomol. Ther.* 23 (2015) 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.4062/biomolther.2014.069>.
- 409 [7] F. Khaleghi, I. Jantan, L.B. Din, W.A. Yaacob, M.A. Khalilzadeh, S.N.A. Bukhari,
410 Immunomodulatory effects of 1-(6-hydroxy-2-isopropenyl-1-benzofuran-5-yl)- 1-ethanone
411 from *Petasites hybridus* and its synthesized benzoxazepine derivatives, *J. Nat. Med.* 68
412 (2014) 351–357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11418-013-0805-9>.
- 413 [8] A. Soleimani, J. Asadi, F. Rostami-Charati, R. Gharaei, High cytotoxicity and apoptotic
414 effects of natural bioactive benzofuran derivative on the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line,
415 *Comb. Chem. High Throughput Screen.* 18 (2015) 505–513.
416 <https://doi.org/10.2174/1386207318666150430114815>.
- 417 [9] B.L. Fiebich, M. Grozdeva, S. Hess, M. Hüll, U. Danesch, A. Bodensieck, R. Bauer,
418 *Petasites hybridus* extracts in vitro inhibit COX-2 and PGE2 release by direct interaction
419 with the enzyme and by preventing p42/44 MAP kinase activation in rat primary microglial
420 cells, *Planta Med.* 71 (2005) 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2005-837744>.
- 421 [10] J. Kleeberg-Hartmann, B. Vogler, K. Messlinger, Petasin and isopetasin reduce CGRP
422 release from trigeminal afferents indicating an inhibitory effect on TRPA1 and TRPV1
423 receptor channels, *J. Headache Pain.* 22 (2021). [https://doi.org/10.1186/s10194-021-01235-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s10194-021-01235-5)
424 5.

- 425 [11] M. Sheykhzade, S. Smajilovic, A. Issa, S. Haunso, S.B. Christensen, J. Tfelt-Hansen, S-
426 petasin and butterbur lactones dilate vessels through blockage of voltage gated calcium
427 channels and block DNA synthesis, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 593 (2008) 79–86.
428 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2008.07.004>.
- 429 [12] A. Bodensieck, O. Kunert, E. Haslinger, R. Bauer, New eremophilane sesquiterpenes from
430 a rhizome extract of *Petasites hybridus*, *Helv. Chim. Acta.* 90 (2007) 183–195.
431 <https://doi.org/10.1002/hlca.200790014>.
- 432 [13] B. Debrunner, M. Neuenschwander, HPLC separation and quantification of the
433 sesquiterpene fraction from *Petasites hybridus* (ger.), *Chimia* 48 (1994) 564–569.
434 <https://doi.org/10.2533/chimia.1994.564>
- 435 [14] K. Skalicka-Woźniak, I. Garrard, A comprehensive classification of solvent systems used
436 for natural product purifications in countercurrent and centrifugal partition chromatography,
437 *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 32 (2015) 1556–1561. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5np00061k>.
- 438 [15] J.-L. Zhong, H. Yan, H.-D. Xu, N. Muhammad, W.-D. Yan, Preparation from *Lepidium*
439 *meyenii* Walpers using high-speed countercurrent chromatography and thermal stability of
440 macamides in air at various temperatures, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 164 (2019) 768–776.
441 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2018.11.041>.
- 442 [16] S.V. Luca, M.E. Czerwińska, A. Miron, A.C. Aprotosoai, L. Marcourt, J.-L. Wolfender, S.
443 Granica, K. Skalicka-Woźniak, High-performance countercurrent chromatographic
444 isolation of acylated iridoid diglycosides from *Verbascum ovalifolium* Donn ex Sims and
445 evaluation of their inhibitory potential on IL-8 and TNF- α production, *J. Pharm. Biomed.*
446 *Anal.* 166 (2019) 295–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2019.01.031>.

- 447 [17] R. Morley, M. Minceva, Liquid–liquid chromatography: current design approaches and
448 future pathways, *Annu. Rev. Chem. Biomol. Eng.* 12 (2021) 495–518.
449 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-chembioeng-101420-033548>.
- 450 [18] G.F. Pauli, S.M. Pro, J.B. Friesen, Countercurrent separation of natural products, *J. Nat.*
451 *Prod.* 71 (2008) 1489–1508. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np800144q>.
- 452 [19] S. Yun Shi, Y. Ping Zhang, K. Long Huang, S. Qin Liu, Y. Zhao, Purification of
453 eremophilane-type sesquiterpenes from *Ligularia atrovioleacea* by high speed countercurrent
454 chromatography, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.* 31 (2008) 828–837.
455 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826070801891296>.
- 456 [20] R. Morley, M. Minceva, Trapping multiple dual mode liquid-liquid chromatography:
457 Preparative separation of nootkatone from a natural product extract, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1625
458 (2020) 461272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461272>.
- 459 [21] A. Frey, E. Hopmann, M. Minceva, Selection of biphasic liquid systems in liquid-liquid
460 chromatography using predictive thermodynamic models, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 37 (2014)
461 1663–1674. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.201400234>.
- 462 [22] E. Hopmann, A. Frey, M. Minceva, A priori selection of the mobile and stationary phase in
463 centrifugal partition chromatography and counter-current chromatography, *J. Chromatogr.*
464 *A* 1238 (2012) 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.03.035>.
- 465 [23] S.V. Luca, S. Roehrer, K. Kleigrew, M. Minceva, Approach for simultaneous cannabidiol
466 isolation and pesticide removal from hemp extracts with liquid-liquid chromatography, *Ind*
467 *Crops Prod.* 155 (2020) 112726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112726>.
- 468 [24] S. Marsden-Jones, N. Colclough, I. Garrard, N. Sumner, S. Ignatova, Using quantitative
469 structure activity relationship models to predict an appropriate solvent system from a

- 470 common solvent system family for countercurrent chromatography separation, J.
471 Chromatogr. A 1398 (2015) 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2015.04.020>.
- 472 [25] L. Marlot, M. Batteau, K. Faure, Classification of biphasic solvent systems according to
473 Abraham descriptors for countercurrent chromatography, J. Chromatogr. A 1617 (2020)
474 460820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2019.460820>.
- 475 [26] J. Brent Friesen, G.F. Pauli, G.U.E.S.S.—A generally useful estimate of solvent systems for
476 CCC, J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol. 28 (2005) 2777–2806.
477 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826070500225234>.
- 478 [27] R. Morley, M. Minceva, Trapping multiple dual mode centrifugal partition chromatography
479 for the separation of intermediately-eluting components: Throughput maximization strategy,
480 J. Chromatogr. A 1501 (2017) 26–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHROMA.2017.04.033>.
- 481 [28] Y. Ito, Golden rules and pitfalls in selecting optimum conditions for high-speed counter-
482 current chromatography, J. Chromatogr. A 1065 (2005) 145–168.
483 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2004.12.044>.
- 484 [29] A. Aebi, J. Buchi, T. Waaler, E. Eichenberger, J. Schmutz, Constituents of *Petasites*
485 *hybridus* (L) FI. Wett. I. (ger.), Pharm. Acta. Helv. 30 (1955) 277–279.
- 486 [30] A. Stoll, R. Morf, A. Rheiner, J. Renz, Über Inhaltsstoffe aus *Petasites officinalis* Moench
487 I. Petasin und die Petasolester B und C, Experientia 12 (1956) 360–362.
488 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02165356>.
- 489 [31] A. Bodensieck, W.M.F. Fabian, O. Kunert, F. Belaj, S. Jahangir, W. Schühly, R. Bauer,
490 Absolute configuration of eremophilane sesquiterpenes from *Petasites hybridus*:
491 Comparison of experimental and calculated circular dichroism spectra, Chirality 22 (2009)
492 308–319. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chir.20743>.

- 493 [32] IUPAC recommendation RF-4.5, (n.d.). <https://iupac.qmul.ac.uk/sectionF/RF45n6.html>
494 (accessed April 26, 2023).
- 495 [33] F. Bohlmann, J. Ziesche, Eremophilane derivatives from *Senecio* species, *Phytochemistry*
496 19 (1980) 2681–2684. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422\(00\)83943-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(00)83943-6).
- 497 [34] T. Matsumoto, D. Imahori, Y. Saito, W. Zhang, T. Ohta, T. Yoshida, Y. Nakayama, E.
498 Ashihara, T. Watanabe, Cytotoxic activities of sesquiterpenoids from the aerial parts of
499 *Petasites japonicus* against cancer stem cells, *J. Nat. Med.* 74 (2020) 689–701.
500 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11418-020-01420-x>.
- 501 [35] M. Tori, M. Kawahara, M. Sono, Eremophilane-type sesquiterpenes from fresh rhizomes of
502 *Petasites japonicus*, *Phytochemistry* 47 (1998) 401–409. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(97)00581-5)
503 9422(97)00581-5.
- 504
- 505

506 **Figure and Table captions**

507

508 **Figure 1.** HPLC-DAD chromatogram of *P. hybridus* extract.

509 **Figure 2.** Liquid-liquid partition equilibria of target petasins (P1-P6) from *P. hybridus* extracts. Labels:

510 total extract concentration in mg/mL; C_{LP} , concentration of the target petasin in the lower phase; C_{UP} ,

511 concentration of the target petasin in the upper phase.

512 **Figure 3.** Influence of the flow-rate (8-16 mL/min) on the stationary phase retention (S_F) in descending

513 mode (DSC), with *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/water (HEMWat) 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v).

514 **Figure 4.** LLC separation of *P. hybridus* extract

515 **Figure 5.** Chemical structures of the isolated petasins

516

517 **Table 1.** Partition coefficients and separation factors of target petasins (P1-P6) from *P. hybridus* extract.

518 **Table 2.** LC-HRMS/MS identification of isolated compounds from *Petasites hybridus* rhizomes.

519 **Table 3.** ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR data of compounds P1-P6 at 500/125 MHz, resp., in methanol- d_4 at 30°C, δ in

520 ppm, J in Hz.

Fig. 1. HPLC-DAD chromatogram of *P. hybridus* extract.

521
522

523

524 **Fig. 2.** Liquid-liquid partition equilibria of target petasins (P1-P6) from *P. hybridus* extracts. Labels: total
 525 extract concentration in mg/mL; C_{LP} , concentration of the target petasin in the lower phase; C_{UP} ,
 526 concentration of the target petasin in the upper phase.

527

528
529 **Fig. 3.** Influence of the flow-rate (8-16 mL/min) on the stationary phase retention (S_F) in descending (DSC)
530 mode, with *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/water (HEMWat) 5/1/5/1 (v/v/v/v).

531

Fig. 4. LLC separation of *P. hybridus* extract

Data are presented as concentration profiles vs. separation time. Points marked in “x” represent the concentrations obtained from the off-line LC-DAD analysis of collected fractions; the curve lines were obtained by fitting the experimental data points into Gaussian equations. Parameters: *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/water (5/1/5/1, v/v/v/v); descending mode (DSC) (lower phase as mobile phase); $V_{column} = 250$ mL; $\omega_{rot} = 1700$ rpm; $F = 10$ mL/min; $V_{inj} = 10$ mL; $\lambda = 230$ nm; $S_F = 0.72$ (measured at the end of the experiment); the feed sample was prepared by dissolving the *P. hybridus* extract in the lower phase at a concentration of 40 mg/mL

532
533
534
535
536
537
538
539
540

Fig. 5. Chemical structures of the isolated petasins

541
542

543

544 **Table 1.** Partition coefficients and separation factors of target petasins (P1-P6) from *P. hybridus* extract.

Solvent system	Partition coefficients						Separation factors					
	v/v	K ₁	K ₂	K ₃	K ₄	K ₅	K ₆	α ₁₂	α ₂₃	α ₃₄	α ₄₅	α ₅₆
HPWat	10/3/7	8.24	>10	>10	>10	>10	>10	nc	nc	nc	nc	nc
	10/4/6	6.72	>10	>10	>10	>10	>10	nc	nc	nc	nc	nc
	10/5/5	4.62	>10	9.18	>10	>10	>10	nc	nc	nc	nc	nc
	10/6/4	4.27	9.40	8.01	>10	>10	>10	2.2	0.9	nc	nc	nc
HMWat	10/7/3	0.08	0.83	1.61	4.29	5.26	6.93	10.4	1.9	2.7	1.2	1.3
	10/7.5/2.5	0.06	0.49	0.93	2.61	2.85	3.63	8.2	1.9	2.8	1.1	1.3
	10/8/2	0.05	0.34	0.64	1.38	1.42	1.39	6.8	1.9	2.2	1.0	1.0
	10/8.5/1.5	0.05	0.23	0.41	0.90	0.90	0.90	4.6	1.8	2.2	1.0	1.0
	10/9/1	0.05	0.19	0.28	0.67	0.67	0.77	3.8	1.5	2.4	1.0	1.1
HEMWat	2/1/2/1	0.44	1.76	1.76	4.31	4.86	4.84	4.0	1.0	2.4	1.1	1.0
	5/2/5/2	0.26	1.02	1.22	2.95	3.04	3.08	3.9	1.2	2.4	1.0	1.0
	3/1/3/1	0.19	0.67	0.82	2.04	2.13	2.18	3.5	1.2	2.5	1.0	1.0
	4/1/4/1	0.15	0.54	0.74	1.66	1.69	1.76	3.6	1.4	2.2	1.0	1.0
	5/1/5/1	0.10	0.36	0.49	1.05	1.08	1.16	3.6	1.4	2.1	1.0	1.1

Abbreviations: HMWat *n*-hexane/methanol/water; HEMWat *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate/methanol/water; HPWat *n*-hexane/1-propanol/water; in bold the selected solvent system

545
546
547

548 **Table 2.** LC-HRMS/MS identification of isolated compounds from *Petasites hybridus* rhizomes.

No	Compound	[M+H] ⁺ _{exp.} (m/z)	[M+H] ⁺ _{calcd.} (m/z)	Δ (ppm)	MF	MS/MS (+)
P1	8β-hydroxyeremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide	251.1657	251.1642	-5.97	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	233.1562, 187.1660, 177.0710, 163.0857, 145.0711, 135.1250, 119.0491, 107.0932, 93.0773
P2	2-[(angeloyl)oxy]eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide	333.2077	333.2060	-5.10	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₄	254.6489, 233.1553, 215.1459, 205.1601, 187.1487, 165.0917, 163.0772, 151.0766, 133.0672, 121.0969, 115.0543, 101.0601
P3	8α/β-H-eremophil-7(11)-en-12,8-olide	235.1690	235.1693	1.28	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂	217.1537, 189.1496, 179.0939, 165.0768, 161.1160, 153.0713, 135.0637, 125.0873, 119.0759, 107.0758, 95.0788, 81.0680
P4	Neopetasin	317.2104	317.2111	2.21	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₃	217.1648, 199.1497, 189.1662, 175.1166, 161.1305, 147.0810, 133.1034, 119.0871, 95.0861
P5	Petasin	317.2091	317.2111	6.30	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₃	217.1508, 199.1362, 189.1572, 175.1012, 161.0883, 147.0720, 133.0575, 123.0771, 119.0796, 101.0563, 95.0778
P6	Isopetasin	317.2123	317.2111	-3.78	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₃	217.1606, 199.1414, 175.1126, 161.0967, 147.0806, 135.1170, 123.0805, 119.0894, 95.0856

549

550 **Table 3.** ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR data of compounds P1-P6 at 500/125 MHz, resp., in methanol-*d*₄ at 30°C, δ in ppm, *J* in Hz.

Position	P1		P2		P3-major		P3-minor		P4		P5		P6	
	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)	δ(C)	δ(H)
1	27.4	1.33 (<i>m</i>) 1.90 (<i>m</i>)	33.1	1.80 (<i>m</i>) 1.92 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.0, 5.0)	27.7	1.38 (<i>m</i>) 1.93 (<i>m</i>)	29.5	1.56 (<i>m</i>) 1.66 (<i>m</i>)	31.5	2.33 (<i>m</i>) 2.68 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.1, 13.1, 5.2, 1.7)	31.6	2.43 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 15.2, 4.7, 2.8) 2.62 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.7, 14.7, 5.3, 1.9)	31.1	2.41 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 15.2, 4.6, 2.6) 2.58 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 15.2, 14.4, 5.2, 2.0)
2	21.7	1.45 (<i>m</i>) 1.45 (<i>m</i>)	70.4	4.98 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.5, 11.5, 5.1, 5.1)	21.7	1.47 (<i>m</i>) 1.57 (<i>m</i>)	21.8	1.47 (<i>m</i>) 1.57 (<i>m</i>)	34.7	2.34 (<i>m</i>)	32.8	1.53 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.3, 11.6, 11.6, 4.5) 2.23 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.2, 4.9, 4.9, 2.7)	32.9	1.53 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.4, 12.1, 11.2, 4.6) 2.21 (<i>dddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.2, 5.2, 4.4, 2.6)
3	31.8	1.29 (<i>m</i>) 1.44 (<i>m</i>)	37.1	1.41 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.7, 12.7, 12.7) 1.82 (<i>m</i>) 1.66 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.0, 6.4, 3.0)	31.9	1.31 (<i>m</i>) 1.44 (<i>m</i>)	30.1	1.45 (<i>m</i>) 1.93 (<i>m</i>)	74.9	5.05 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 10.9, 10.9, 4.8)	74.5	5.01 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.1, 11.1, 4.4)	74.7	4.96 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.1, 11.1, 4.4)
4	30.8	1.46 (<i>m</i>)	30.7	1.66 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.0, 6.4, 3.0)	31.3	1.46 (<i>m</i>)	39.8	1.60 (<i>m</i>)	44.9	2.02 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 10.7, 6.7)	48.7	1.67 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.1, 6.7)	47.6	1.72 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.1, 6.7)
5	41.4	- 2.07 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.6, 1.6)	40.3	-	41.2	-	40.8	-	41.3	-	41.4	-	43.6	-
6	35.9	2.84 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.6)	36.2	2.06 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.2, 1.6) 2.99 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.2)	37.1	1.95 (<i>ddt</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.1, 2.7, 1.1) 2.97 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.1)	34.8	2.20 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.0, 1.6) 2.96 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.8)	38.8	2.02 (<i>m</i>) 2.07 (<i>m</i>)	43.0	1.95 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.4, 13.1, 0.6) 2.07 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.1, 4.7)	42.2	2.22 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.8, 0.8) 3.03 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.8)
7	161.4	-	163.4	-	164.3	-	166.2	-	51.5	3.14 (<i>m</i>)	51.5	3.23 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 14.4, 4.6)	128.3	-
8	105.8	-	81.8	4.76 (<i>ddq</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.1, 6.7, 1.4)	82.3	4.77 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.0, 3.0)	80.0	4.96 (<i>ddq</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.5, 7.6, 1.1) 1.55 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.7, 11.5, 4.7)	201.6	-	201.1	-	193.8	-
9	40.1	1.95 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.4, 4.4) 1.99 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.4, 12.8)	36.8	1.64 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 13.0, 13.0, 11.1) 2.28 (<i>ddd</i> , <i>J</i> = 12.6, 6.7, 3.5)	36.3	1.74 (<i>m</i>) 2.08 (<i>m</i>)	36.7	1.83 (<i>br d</i> , <i>J</i> = 11.7)	124.3	-	125.1	-	127.1	-
10	41.1	1.88 (<i>m</i>)	42.0	1.95 (<i>m</i>)	41.4	1.74 (<i>m</i>)	37.6	-	171.3	-	170.1	-	168.8	-
11	123.0	-	121.6	-	121.1	-	122.2	-	145.0	-	144.7	-	145.7	-
12	174.6	-	177.1	-	177.3	-	177.3	-	114.2	4.73 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 2.1, 1.0) 4.91 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 1.5)	114.8	4.82 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 0.8) 4.94 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 1.5)	22.3	1.90 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.4)

13	8.2	1.79 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6)	8.2	1.80 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6, 1.6)	8.2	1.78 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6, 1.6)	7.9	1.76 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.7, 1.7)	20.9	1.76 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 0.8)	20.2	1.71 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 0.8)	22.8	2.07 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 2.1)
14	16.5	0.84 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.6)	16.3	0.91 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.7)	16.5	0.83 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.6)	15.8	1.05 (<i>dd</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 0.6)	12.0	1.01 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.7)	10.9	0.99 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.7)	11.2	1.03 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 6.7)
15	21.9	1.07 (<i>s</i>)	21.8	1.12 (<i>s</i>)	21.9	1.07 (<i>s</i>)	25.1	0.82 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.0)	21.4	1.21 (<i>s</i>)	17.3	1.30 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 0.6)	17.6	1.09 (<i>d</i> , <i>J</i> = 0.8)
1'			169.1	-							169.0	-	169.1	-
2'			129.5	-							129.2	-	129.2	-
3'			138.2	6.07 (<i>qq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.3, 1.6)						6.12 (<i>qq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.5)	138.8	6.12 (<i>qq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.5)	138.8	6.12 (<i>qq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.6)
4'			15.9	1.93 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.6)						1.96 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.6)	15.9	1.96 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.5)	15.9	1.96 (<i>dq</i> , <i>J</i> = 7.2, 1.6)
5'			20.6	1.84 (<i>qd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6, 1.6)						1.88 (<i>qd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6, 1.6)	20.7	1.88 (<i>qd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.5, 1.5)	20.7	1.88 (<i>qd</i> , <i>J</i> = 1.6, 1.6)

551 * The atom numbering of CH₃(14) and CH₃(15) in this publication follows the IUPAC recommendation RF-4.5, URL:

552 <https://iupac.qmul.ac.uk/sectionF/RF45n6.html>

553